

“OPEN ACCESS TRAINING MATERIAL FOR TEACHERS AND RESEARCHERS”

D5.3: “OA training material for teachers and researchers”

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CITIZEN SCIENCE: AN INTRODUCTORY GUIDE FOR TEACHERS

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List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
STEAM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
M	month
D	deliverable
MS	milestone

1. Introduction

This deliverable is a comprehensive guide aimed at empowering teachers across Europe to integrate **Citizen Science** into their classrooms, offering both theoretical insights and practical applications. Citizen science, the practice of engaging the public in scientific research, serves as a dynamic pedagogical tool to foster inquiry-based learning, critical thinking, and active participation among pupils. This resource outlines the principles of Citizen Science, its alignment with educational frameworks, and its potential to make learning more engaging and relevant. Teachers will learn how to incorporate Citizen Science activities into their curricula, leveraging real-world data collection and analysis to bridge the gap between classroom theory and global scientific challenges. Practical examples of Citizen Science projects suitable for children are given. By participating in Citizen Science projects, pupils not only enhance their STEAM skills but also develop a deeper sense of social responsibility and global awareness.

2. What is Citizen Science?

How to help people to properly inform themselves, understand and face collective choices in full awareness? Are science, involvement, and bottom-up participation reconcilable ideas?

The recent pandemic highlighted the scepticism in public opinion towards science: now more than ever we need correct and reliable scientific communication, and we need to find a common ground between the scientists and the public to increase their awareness of the scientific method and their involvement in collective choices.

Moreover, several global crises are now posing a challenge to all societies around the world, but “*there are scientific recommendations, but no social consensus for implementation*”¹: the loss of biodiversity, climate change, and emerging zoonotic diseases need **the commitment and efforts of everyone**, policymakers, industry, science, and civil society included, to ensure healthy and resilient societies.

The connection between science and society is therefore an increasingly crucial factor for a democratic development that allows citizens to make the proper choices for their lives and for the society itself. *Citizen Science* or “**science made by citizens**” can help citizens to understand and share not only the meaning and the value of scientific research, but also its effects in everyday life and for a good standard of living, especially when applied to the local context in which citizens live. Citizen Science is therefore **a tool** that can connect different spheres of society and **a bona fide scientific methodology** that, when done correctly, has the potential to influence important policy decisions.

The **definition of Citizen Science** given by the European Commission is ²:

1. European Commission (2022), The transformative potential of Citizen Science, Magazine of European Research Council, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/transformative-potential-citizen-science>

2. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation - European Commission Citizen Science, 2020, Elevating research and innovation through societal engagement, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d1768147-f17a-11ea-991b-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-152465380>

/ˈsɪt.i.zən ˌsaɪ.əns/

“ Citizen Science is the voluntary participation of non-professional scientists in research and innovation, at different stages of the process and at different levels of engagement: from defining research programs and policies to collecting, processing and analyzing data and evaluating research results. ”

In parallel with the process of democratisation of science, Citizen Science plays a revolutionary role in disrupting the *ivory tower paradigm*, that posits that true knowledge can be achieved only in research institutes or universities. This paradigm is reductive and not inclusive, failing to recognize that many usable notions are available outside the academia. The process of accepting the value of Citizen Science is still being in progress, but scientists are finally recognizing its importance and benefits. The *conditio sine qua non* for a Citizen Science project is therefore that researchers exercise a certain degree of “humility” to step back and learn from others, resulting in a mutually beneficial relationship between science and society.

Citizen Science isn't just a buzzword...

- It's a movement, a collaboration between passionate individuals, coming together to contribute our knowledge, skills, and curiosity to scientific endeavours.
- It's about harnessing the power of collective intelligence to solve real-world problems.
- Citizen Science has the potential to revolutionize how we approach scientific discovery, making it more inclusive, diverse, and impactful.

2.1 Pillars of Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI)

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) engages public and accountable stakeholders to achieve research and innovation results that are:

- Ethically acceptable
- Sustainable
- Socially desirable

The rationale behind RRI is that science and technology have the potential to change the future, but this can happen if citizens, industry, and other societal stakeholders are involved in the process.

RRI is based on 6 pillars that are: Public Engagement, Open Science, Research Integrity and Ethics, Science education, Gender equality, and Governance (Figure 1) ³. Accordingly, core principles for responsibly conducting research and innovation are anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion, responsiveness, openness, and transparency.

Figure 1 – Six pillars of RRI.

3. D.-G. for R. and I. European Commission, Responsible research and innovation: Europe's ability to respond to societal challenges, (2014). <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2be36f74-b490-409e-bb60-12fd438100fe/language-en/format-PDF/source-search>

Citizen Science is positioned at the interface between Public Engagement and Open Science (Figure 1), but it can also incorporate all 6 dimensions of RRI ⁴:

Public Engagement, engaging citizens and other stakeholders to collaborate within the research and innovation ecosystem and address social challenges;

Open Science, making science accessible and unrestricted;

Integrity and ethics of research, linking research to the 10 principles of Citizen Science and considering related ethical issues;

Gender equality, promoting gender balance and the inclusion of gender and sex issues in research and Innovation, and all participatory activities, including communication used to engage women;

Science education, encouraging scientific literacy and critical thinking, and promoting STEAM (Science Technology Engineering Art and Maths) careers;

Governance, fostering liaisons with legislators to encourage official use of citizen-generated data and evidence-based policies.

4. Adapted from Rosa Arias, *The Citizen Science Funding Landscape*, TIME4CS webinar 9.3.23

2.2 Ten principles of Citizen Science

In 2015 the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) promoted the drafting of the *10 principles of Citizen Science*⁵, with the aim of finding common aspects and guidelines valid for all initiatives and these ten principles have been translated into the 27 languages of the European Union, to give them the greatest possible dissemination.

Here the 10 principles:

1. Citizen Science projects actively involve citizens in scientific endeavour that generates **new knowledge or understanding**. Citizens may act as contributors, collaborators, or as project leader and have a meaningful role in the project.
2. Citizen Science projects have a **genuine science outcome**. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy.
3. **Both the professional scientists and the Citizen Scientists benefit from taking part**. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy.
4. Citizen Scientists may, if they wish, participate **in multiple stages** of the scientific process. This may include developing the research question, designing the method, gathering and analysing data, and communicating the results.
5. Citizen Scientists **receive feedback** from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are.
6. Citizen Science is considered a research approach like any other, with limitations and biases that should be considered and controlled for. However, unlike traditional research approaches, Citizen Science provides **opportunity for greater public engagement and democratisation of science**.
7. Citizen **Science project data and meta-data are made publicly available** and where possible, results are published in an open access format. Data sharing may occur during or after the project, unless there are security or privacy concerns that prevent this.
8. Citizen Scientists are acknowledged in project results and publications.
9. Citizen Science programmes are evaluated for their scientific output, **data quality**, participant experience and wider societal or **policy impact**.
10. The leaders of Citizen Science projects **take into consideration legal and ethical issues** surrounding copyright, intellectual property, data sharing agreements, confidentiality, attribution, and the environmental impact of any activities.

5. European Citizen Science Association, 2015, *Ten Principles of Citizen Science*, <http://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XPR2N>

2.3. How many Citizen Science projects?

The forms of Citizen Science that we see today are very different from the past. In fact, it is now an activity that can be **carried out by everyone**, whereas once it was only for few interested individuals⁶. From the initial collaborative role in data collection, citizens have now also participated in the formulation of research questions, the creation of methods and the analysis of the data themselves⁷. The ways in which citizens participate in projects can be many: some make their own local resources available (such as, for example, their backyard), others share the computational resources of their PCs, and still others provide their cognitive skills in data analysis.

Citizen Science has spread in recent years mainly due to advances in technology, particularly the Internet and mobile devices as these tools have made it easy for people to contribute using specific Apps and share their observations⁸ generating data that would otherwise be difficult or expensive to obtain⁹.

Citizen Science projects can therefore be classified according to **volunteer engagement**¹⁰ (figure 2), usually paralleled by a decrease in the leadership and control played on the project by the “professional” researchers.

6. Silvertown, J. (2009) *A new dawn for Citizen Science*. Trends in Ecology, Evolution 24(9): 467-471, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.03.017>.

7. Cooper, C.B., Lewenstein, B.V. (2016) *Two meanings of Citizen Science*. in Cavalier, D., Kennedy E.B. (Eds.) *The Rightful Place of Science: Citizen science*, pp. 51-62, AZ: Consortium for Science, Policy, Outcomes, Tempe

8. Newman, G., Wiggins, A., Crall, A., Graham, G., Newman, S., Crowston, K. (2012) *The future of Citizen Science: Emerging technologies and shifting paradigms*, Front Ecol Environment 6(10): 298-304. <https://doi.org/10.1890/110294>.

9. Cohn, J.P. (2008) *Citizen science: Can Volunteers Do Real Research?*, BioScience 58(3): 192–197. <https://doi.org/10.1641/B580303>

10. Haklay, M. (2013) *Citizen Science and Volunteered Geographic Information: Overview and Typology of Participation*, Crowdsourcing Geogr. Knowl., Springer Netherlands, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-4587-2_7

Figure 2 – Classification of Citizen Science projects according to volunteer engagement and four illustrative projects^{11,12,13,14}

11. <https://www.mountainow.net/en/>

12. <https://www.thekidstrial.ie/>

13. <https://www.citieshealth.eu/>

14. Peplow, M. (2018) *The Flint water crisis: how citizen scientists exposed poisonous politics*, 559: 180
<https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-05651-7>

According to the type of project, not only can the percentage of volunteer engagement vary, but also which kind of data is collected ¹⁵ (figure 3).

Figure 3 – Collection of data in Citizen Science projects

Obviously, the more people participate, the more accurate the data will be, corroborating the chances of an accurate answer to the scientific problem investigated and reducing the probability of biased observations. Moreover, a vast amount of data can be collected in a shorter time.

A well-constructed protocol for the project is of utmost importance: Citizen Science is a scientific approach like any other and therefore it is at its best when it is specific, that is, when the question to be addressed is clear¹⁵. In this way citizens or students can collect data of comparable quality to the data collected by professionals ¹⁶⁻¹⁷.

15. Pocock, M.J.O., Chapman, D.S., Sheppard, L.J. & Roy, H.E. (2014). *Choosing and Using Citizen Science: a guide to when and how to use citizen science to monitor biodiversity and the environment*. Centre for Ecology & Hydrology https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/sepa_choosingandusingcitizenscience_interactive_4web_final_amended-blue1.pdf

16. Crall, A. W., Newman, G. J., Stohlgren, T. J., Holfelder, K. A., Graham, J., & Waller, D. M. (2011). *Assessing citizen science data quality: An invasive species case study*. *Conservation Letters*, 4(6), 433–442. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-263X.2011.00196.x>

17. Lewandowski, E., Caldwell, W., Elmquist, D., & Oberhauser, K. (2017). *Public Perceptions of Citizen Science*. *Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*, 2(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.77>

3. Why Citizen Science in Europe?

Citizen Science is gaining more and more ground in Europe, with projects paying special attention to environmental issues. A recent study¹⁸ provides interesting data on this growing trend. The study analysed 157 Citizen Science projects in Europe participating in the Horizon 2020 program, mainly from Spain (37%), Portugal (17%) and Italy (11%). The results show that most projects focus on environment and land issues (66.5%), with a particular focus on biodiversity (35.6%).

European Commission contributes to foster and finance Citizens Science projects¹⁹ because they are characterized by:

3.1. Excellence:

- They broaden the scope of R&I and the quality and quantity of data collected, discussed and analysed
- They increase the robustness of results
- They enable innovative and creative approaches
- They harness collective intelligence (often excluded from contributing to Research & Innovation)

3.2. Effectiveness:

- They align results with society's needs, values and expectations, ensuring greater relevance and adoption
- They reduce time-to-market for innovative products and services
- They trigger behavioural changes

3.3. Rise in society's trust in science

- They increase openness, transparency and 'co-ownership' of society
- They often lead to more inclusive outcomes
- They encourage mutual learning between science and society

18. Giardullo, P., Neresini, F., Marín-González, E., Luís, C., Magalhães, J. and Arias, R. (2023). *Citizen Science and participatory science communication: an empirically informed discussion connecting research and theory*, Journal of Science Communication, <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.22020201>

19. Farrer, L, Delaney N., 27-10-2021, *Citizen and societal engagement: A policy and programme priority for the European Commission*, EU-Citizen Science event, <https://eu-citizen.science/static/site/files/Citizen%20and%20societal%20engagement%20-%20Niamh%20Delaney%20and%20Linden%20Farrer.pdf>

4. Why Citizen Science in schools?

4.1 Three main reasons for embracing Citizen Science in your teaching

1. Citizen Science offers new educational perspectives

Students can develop a greater interest in science, collecting meaningful, real-world data and improving their understanding of the scientific method.

Moreover, on one side students may offer different perspectives from adult scientists and being involved in a Citizen Science project can help them understand new way of thinking about problems; on the other side scientists could make use of data collected by students to study real problems.

With Citizen Science everybody is rewarded: **citizens become researchers and researchers increase their sense of citizenship.**

2. Citizen Science helps the development of cross-cutting principles in schools

EMPOWERMENT

The sense of control and responsibility that participants assume during the project for oneself and for the environment involved. It is strengthened both by the collaborative approaches used in Citizen Science and the addressing of community problems of a project.

CO-CREATION

The collaborative process in which multiple actors (citizens, stakeholders, researchers) use methods and tools for working together without a hierarchical scale.

CHANGEMAKING

Transformations that invest communities and in a wider range cultures and institutions. It leads to a change also in attitudes, values and consciousness.

OPENNESS

Increase in the transparency of data, protocols and actions.

Figure 4 - Cross-cutting principles in schools developed by Citizen Science

3. Citizen Science goes beyond outreach and Public Engagement

As the first of the 10 principles of Citizen Science goes, *Citizen Science projects actively engage citizens in scientific activities that generate new knowledge or understanding*. Public Engagement initiatives *actively engage citizens in scientific activities* as well (figure 5). However, Citizen Science initiatives *actually generate new knowledge or understanding* (figure 6).

Figure 5 - Public Engagement²⁰

Figure 6 - Citizen Science²¹

As mentioned above, Citizen Science is a *de facto* research methodology. Just like any other one therefore, it has advantages and limitations: in a research laboratory, all conditions are controlled, which allows causal conclusions to be drawn. In the real world, we can reach communities that would probably never come in the laboratory. The strength lies in the combination of methods, where the limitations of one method can be offset by the advantages of another ²² .

20. Image by zinkevych on Freepik

21. Image from: <https://www.openaire.eu/blogs/university-approaches-to-citizen-science-in-the-transition-to-open-science>

22. Crone, E., 2022, *Knowledge is everywhere*, European Research Council Magazine, <https://erc.europa.eu/news-events/magazine-article/knowledge-everywhere>

4.2 Project Based Learning and Citizen Science

Citizen Science is a valuable teaching tool that enables students to become aware of many current issues, to understand the value of participating in a community for the common good²³, but most importantly to affect **the meaning of disciplinary content**, often learned in school in a de-contextualized way. Citizen Science shares many features with **Project-Based Learning (PBL)**²⁴, a teaching method in which students can face real-world problems, growing up in their critical thinking skill. Meaningful projects for the community are the common ground where Citizen Science in schools and teaching methodologies meet.

The theoretical background of Project-Based Learning is characterized by four major driving ideas:

1. **Active construction:** students are pushed to construct their knowledge in real-world activities similar to those that experts live daily and to solve problems.
2. **Situated learning:** students experience phenomena throughout the implementation of a PBL project by designing investigations, explaining, modelling, and presenting their ideas to others. As a result, students can understand the link between new information acquired during the data collection, what was known before the data collection, and the conceptual framing of the inquiry.
3. **Social interactions:** students share and debate with others on the issue identified in the project, creating a sense of community of learners.
4. **Cognitive tools:** students acquire new skills related to technologies usually used by scientists and that are specific for the collection of scientific data, visualization and data analysis, planning and testing models, developing documents and infographics to share results and disseminate.

A Project-Based Classroom allows therefore students to investigate questions, following the inquiry method of scientists: proposing hypotheses and discussing how something can be tested and improved. This process results in the acquisition or corroboration of soft skills, such as: team building and working together, facing uncertain situations, seeking new ways out of comfort zone, acceptance of mistakes and failures as part of the process needed to ameliorate in the future.

23. Shah, H.R., Martinez, L.R. (2016). *Current Approaches in Implementing Citizen Science in the Classroom*. Journal of Microbiology, Biology Education, <https://doi.org/10.1128/jmbe.v17i1.1032>

24. Adapted from Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit, an online course on <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science/course/view.php?id=35>

The correspondence between Citizen Science steps and the features of PBL is as follows (figure 7)²⁵:

Figure 7 - The correspondence between Citizen Science steps and the features of PBL

25. Krajcik JS, Blumenfeld PC. Project Based Learning (2014), The Cambridge Handbook of the Learning Sciences. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139519526.018>

4.3. Example of Citizen Science projects at school

Here is a list of Citizen Science projects selected by the MMS teams suitable for pupils:

- **StallCatchers** is an online game suitable for everyone from 6 to 99 years old. In the game, you look at movies from the brains of mice and try to identify vessels as flowing or stalled. This helps to speed up Alzheimer's disease research at Cornell University: in 1 hour of gaming the community of StallCatchers can produce the same amount of data that requires a researcher 5 days in the lab²⁶.
- **Stomycraft** is a video game, developed by Federazione delle Associazioni Incontinenti e Stomizzati (FAIS, the Italian federation of incontinent and ostomised people), that teaches ostomised children to manage the ostomy pouch while facing enemies and building new worlds. They participate in various challenges with their caregiver and cultivate mutual trust together. Moreover, they can play with people from all over the world, meet new friends and safely share doubts²⁷.
- **Colony B** is a puzzle mobile game developed at McGill University in which players are in charge of growing a colony of bacteria, which accumulate to survive. The goal is to identify clusters of bacteria that are accumulating: clusters generate points based on their density and allow in turn to grow the players' colonies. The results are used to analyze data from the American Gut Project based at the University of California San Diego²⁸.
- **Eyewire** is a game to map the brain. Hundreds of thousands of people from around the world, with no need for a scientific background, are mapping the 3D structure of neurons and advancing the quest to understand ourselves²⁹.
- **EteRNA** is a browser-based "game with a purpose" that lets players solve puzzles related to the folding of RNA molecules. The goal is to help find RNA molecules that are biologically active³⁰.
- **Globe at Night** is an international Citizen Science campaign, developed by NASA, to raise public awareness of the impact of light pollution by inviting Citizen Scientists to measure & submit their night sky brightness observations³¹.
- **Foldscope** is a paper microscope that combines low-cost materials with precision optics. This innovation results in microscopes that are both high-quality and affordable. The microscopes have a range of magnifications (50X-340X), allowing the visualization of tiny microorganisms to larger samples like insects, plants, fabrics, and tissues. Foldscope can also attach to mobile phones for imaging and is very portable, durable, and waterproof³².
- **GLOBE Clouds** is an app-based tool, sponsored by NASA, which will help the Citizen Scientists document what they see in the sky. Through the GLOBE Observer app, they can report on overall cloud cover and surface conditions that can impact satellite observations, cloud types, cloud opacity, sky conditions and visibility, and they can upload photos of what they see in the sky³³.
- **Sourdough for Science** is a project in which Citizen Scientists create a sourdough starter by mixing flour and water, then track its growth over two weeks by measuring its height and pH. By participating, they contribute their data to a larger scientific study, helping to uncover how different flours impact microbial growth and, ultimately, the flavour and texture of the bread. Additional modules include

26. <https://stallcatchers.com/>

27. <https://stomycraft.org/>

28. <http://csb.cs.mcgill.ca/colonyb/>

29. <https://eyewire.org/explore>

30. <https://www.citizenscience.gov/eterna/#>

31. <https://globeatnight.org/>

32. <https://foldscope.com/>

33. <https://observer.globe.gov/>

exploring variables that influence starter growth, graphing collected data, and learning about common sourdough microbes³⁴.

- **ESA IMPACT** is an immersive sci-fi game set on the Moon, in which players build and manage a lunar base, generating valuable scientific data along the way. They analyse and annotate craters on actual satellite images of the moon, aiding the European Space Agency (ESA) in mapping the lunar surface, and potentially assisting in future moon landings and research³⁵.

4.4 Teacher Perspectives and Challenges

A recent study explored teachers' knowledge, experience, and interest in incorporating Citizen Science into their teaching³⁶. The research involved a **questionnaire** completed by 355 primary and secondary **school teachers** across Australia, highlighting on the role of Citizen Science in education.

The results were encouraging: over half of the teachers were familiar with the concept of Citizen Science, and about 40% had already introduced such projects in their classrooms. These initiatives often included activities like environmental data collection, naturalistic observations and participation in genuine scientific research - earning positive feedback for their engagement and impact.

However, despite its potential, introduction of Citizen Science into classrooms, presents notable challenges. Teachers pointed to gaps in knowledge, limited time and a lack of confidence, alongside concerns about aligning Citizen Science projects with the national curriculum.

Interestingly, 92% of respondents indicated that **curriculum-aligned projects** would motivate them to adopt Citizen Science more widely in their classrooms. To ensure that Citizen Science evolves beyond being a sporadic activity, it must seamlessly integrate with local school curriculums. This guarantees its sustained relevance and effectiveness in student learning experiences.

34. <http://studentsdiscover.org/lesson/sourdough-for-science/>

35. <https://blogs.esa.int/exploration/gaming-to-the-moon/>

36. Braz Sousa L, Kenneally C, Golumbic Y, Martin JM, Preston C, Rutledge P, et al. (2024) *Teacher experiences and understanding of citizen science in Australian classrooms*. PLoS OE 19(11): e0312680.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0312680>

5. How to implement Citizen Science in schools

5.1 The six phases for Citizen Science implementation in schools

There are **six main phases** ³⁷ that can be identified and are distinguished by timing, duration, main actors involved, and objectives (figure 7): 1) Definition of scope; 2) Planning; 3) Sensing or data collection; 4) Awareness; 5) Reflections; 6) Legacy.

Figure 8 - Phases of Citizen Science at school

Each phase is crucial: this is why we provide here a list of “guiding questions for teachers” that teachers can tick, ensuring that phase has been completed in the right way. Figures below are therefore a package of implementing- guiding lines for teachers.

37. Adapted from *Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit*, an online course on <https://moodle.eu-citizen.science/course/view.php?id=35>

Phase 1 – Definition of scope

Figure 9 – Phase 1 of Citizen Science at school

Phase 2 – Planning

Figure 10 – Phase 2 of Citizen Science at school

Phase 3 – Sensing and data collection

Figure 11 – Phase 3 of Citizen Science at school

Phase 4 – Awareness

Figure 12 – Phase 4 of Citizen Science at school

Phase 5 – Reflections

Reflections

 Throughout the process, especially after sensing and data collection

To look back and improve

If more activities are planned in the future, it is essential to understand what worked well and what could be improved (i.e. a different method or device). It is a moment of active participation to criticize activities.

DURATION

 Planning a gathering to celebrate what has been accomplished during the project can help providing a sort of closure

MAIN ACTORS

 Everyone involved (in particular students). Changes in devices or collecting methods should be proposed by teachers, students or researchers.

GUIDING QUESTIONS FOR TEACHERS

- Which is students' feedback about the experience?
- Were students able to use devices provided? Or proposed data difficult to collect?
- Did the core team need to make the planning phase last longer?
- How have students' knowledge and feelings changed over the course of the project?

This stage can be represented with Double Diamond design process. The figure is based on Design Council's Double Diamond. Arrows stands for reflection phase that is throughout the process.

Figure 13 – Phase 5 of Citizen Science at school

Phase 6 – Legacy

Figure 14 – Phase 6 of Citizen Science at school

5.2 Some useful tools

We suggest here a series of tools that can be used by teachers and researchers to make their activities more engaging and pluralistic.

To collect feedback, co-create, collaborate and stimulate criticism³⁸:

- Google Jamboard ³⁹
- Miroboard ⁴⁰
- Padlet ⁴¹
- Mural ⁴²
- Mentimeter ⁴³
- Slido ⁴⁴
- Wooclap ⁴⁵

To analyse and visualize data in other devices:

- Google sheets ⁴⁶
- Data Wrapper ⁴⁷
- Canva ⁴⁸

38. These tools can be used both on LIM and projector. LIM is an acronym of the italian Lavagna Interattiva Multimediale, it is an interactive surface, similar to blackboard, on which it is possible to write, draw, attach images, display text, play videos or animations. The content displayed and processed on the whiteboard can then be digitized using specially dedicated presentation software.

39. <https://jamboard.google.com/>

40. <https://miro.com/>

41. <https://padlet.com/>

42. <https://www.mural.co/>

43. <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

44. <https://www.slido.com/>

45. <https://www.wooclap.com/>

46. <https://workspace.google.com/intl/it/products/sheets/>

47. <https://www.datawrapper.de/>

48. <https://www.canva.com/graphs/>

5.3. Conclusion and some tips

Citizen Science projects are based on a teaching/learning model that provides participants with all the tools, **both conceptual and material**, they need to correctly interpret the reality around them through the scientific method, which is, by its very nature, highly structured and based on data and evidence. This in turn will help students forming a skill, **critical thinking**, applicable then to any life or work context ⁴⁹. Indeed, critical thinking is especially important in this day and age considering the onslaught of information and disinformation from various sources, including social media,

Final tips

Here are our final tips for implementing a Citizen Science project in your school:

1. Don't assume that a Citizen Science project must be started by researchers: schools themselves can propose a project or a set of driving questions. Schools are encouraged to seek out stakeholders who can support these ideas and provide operational expertise if needed, creating a collaborative framework around their needs and objectives.
2. The European Citizen Science platform <https://eu-citizen.science/> is an excellent resource for project ideas and inspiration, as well as a source for finding existing Citizen Science projects that schools can join.
3. If you come across a Citizen Science project in a school and wish to replicate it, feel free to tailor the project to fit your unique context, adapting it to your school curriculum. Project designs often evolve during implementation, influenced by a range of factors, some of which may be unforeseen.

49. Caruso, J.P., Israel, N., Rowland, K., Lovelace, M.J., Saunders, M.J. (2016). Citizen science: The small world initiative improved lecture grades and California critical thinking skills test scores of nonscience major students at Florida Atlantic University. *Journal of microbiology, biology education* 17(1): 156-162.